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“THE HUGE TREE”

There was a married couple who were so popular and successful. The husband's name was Emanuel; he was handsome, strong, and ingratitudes. The wife's name was Nora; she was a pretty and envious woman. They live in a huge mansion.

One day, Emanuel told his wife that he would be gone in two weeks because of a business trip. As he left for his trip, he told his wife "Take care of the house while I'm gone"
Nora replied "Alright, dear".

Two weeks passed. Nora was doing household chores, but suddenly a knock was heard. "Who's outside?"
"Nora questionably mumbled to herself, so she went and opened the door. When she opened the door, she saw her old friend Isabell weeping. Nora told Isabell, "What on earth! What are you doing here?" Nora angrily asked.

"Please, Nora, I need your help," Isabell replied.

On the other hand, Emanuel's ship has already arrived. He got into his car and drove to his house. When he arrived, he saw his wife shouting and Isabell weeping. So, he went straight to where Isabell and Nora are and asked, "What's happening here?"

"This girl said she needs our help," Nora sarcastically replied.

Emanuel laughs sarcastically; he says, "In your dreams, you ugly woman".

"Get lost! or I'll drag you outside." Isabell had no choice, so she left the couple's house.

Isabell was shocked when a doctor rushed up to her upon her arrival at the hospital and exclaimed, "Ma'am, your son is getting weak, and it is worsening!"

Isabell dropped on her knees in response. She got to her feet, dashed to the neighboring church, and entered to pray. Isabell said. "Lord, please assist my son; I can't stand to see him suffer."

Somehow an elderly man heard her prayer and responded, "Don't worry, sweetheart, your son will be better soon."

Weeks went by, her son recovered his health, and they were content in their home. The couple, on the other hand, had a violent earthquake, which caused them to lose their home and become homeless. As a result, they spent the night sleeping on the street. The following day, they saw that their skin started to alter. When Nora started to fear, Emanuel held her and gradually transformed into a massive tree.

